

Enhancing Productivity through Human Resources Training: Literature Review

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Abstract:- This paper presents a discussion on the importance of training in the success of organisations. Considering the permanent and unavoidable changes in the immediate environment of any organisation, training is the only way organisations can learn new skills and practices which can allow the smooth adoption of the new practices to fit the new environments and meet their goals. However, the achievement of success in any training will depend on a number of factors which help the knowledge and skills to perform a specific activity to be acquired (Reid, 1996). De Silva (1997) noted that training is meant to transfer information and knowledge from the source (trainer) to the trainees (employees). It is worth to note that training should be considered along with organisation's education policies and systems meant for human development. It is therefore, from this point that every organisation should have a well-defined structured training curriculum (Mensah 2018). More importantly, consideration should be on the pedagogy which would be used in the process of training and learning. Employee training is necessary when there is a noted deficiency on the employee's performance. Training can therefore be termed as an ongoing process to help employees perform a particular work much better from the day they work (Donnelly Dalal-Clayton and Hughes (1998) refer to training as a process designed to improve employees' skills and competencies to do certain job. Being referred to a process effective training is supposed to follow a well-defined criterion and with the support of right pedagogical.

Keywords:- Training, Human Resources, Productivity

I. INTRODUCTION

The main goals and objectives of most profit making organisation globally are centred on increasing wealth for the shareholders and adequate human resources systems must be in place to enhance the organisation's performance and hence increase the wealth (Rodriguez 2017). Mwema and gachunga (2014) assert that employees are the backbone of any organisation and as such the accomplishment of goals and objectives are hinged on the organisation's employees. Human resources management is a strategic and logical approach to the management of this valuable asset known as employees. As the employees determine the organisation's achievement of goals and objectives, the human resources management (HRM) is designed to maximise employees' performance through its various functions amongst which is training. This paper seeks to determine how training as part of the HRM functions can enhance productivity in organisations.

II. DEFINING PROFESSIONAL TRAINING AND ITS PHASES

Borrowing the words of Cole (1993:362), he defined professional training as "any type of activity that targets an acquisition of knowledge and skills that are specific to the purposes of certain trade or to a task". Emilia (1999:162) was more focused on sustainability when he defined it as "a learning/instructive process by which employees acquire theoretic and practical knowledge, new abilities or techniques that improves the efficiency level of their performance". Terms such as vocational training and professional development sometimes come to replace professional training. However, Chisu (2002:354) in an effort to differentiate the two terms has the following to say, "Personnel vocational training consists of the sum of the actions used by employees to acquire within an organised setup an array of knowledge, skills, certain manners and behaviours that are required for several specific tasks for the company and professional development is said to consists of a number of actions by which employees, who followed certain programs hold in the company, improve their skills, knowledge, aptitudes, manners, behaviours and working techniques for which they are already qualified, all for the purpose of achieving a superior level of their goals and tasks"

III. IMPORTANCE OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING IN AN ORGANISATION

For any organisation to remain competitive, it should ensure that the level of the services or products provided need to be maintained at least at a satisfactory level or even more. It has been proven that employees' professional training is one important activity which needs to be taken and supported at the managerial level of an organisation. Professional training has the effect to improve organisational employees and more so it assists to employees to readjust to the permanent changes that are unavoidable in certain adjacent environments to that organisation

Despite the some Organisations are non-profit making, the services they provide to the citizens should be continuously improved to maintain satisfactory level and remain competitive in terms of the services provided. This has therefore, made all managers to gain more interest in permanently providing education and training to their organisations' personnel. When well implemented, the education and training does ensure a proper execution of professional tasks ending with higher level performance.

This is supported by the words of Kratcoski and Das (2007:4) when they said,

“Education was viewed as developing the ability to conceptualise and expand theoretical and analytic learning process, while training involved gaining the skills needed to accomplish the immediate tasks and goals of police operations”.

According to the above explanation, the goals of the organisation are easily accomplished if the education and training is effective.

IV. HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT AND PRODUCTIVITY

Suwandej (2015) avers that successful organisation who have five key aspects of HRM one of which is appropriate training of employees. Successful organisations are obviously the ones that that meet their goals and objectives in terms of productivity which results in profit maximisation. De Koeijer et.al (as cited in Arulrajah 2017) postulates that HRM is a very important and necessary element in enhancing productivity in organisations. This is because HRM has the responsibility to ensure that employees are recruited accordingly as per the qualifications needed, employees are happy and they work under conducive environment as well as ensuring that they are motivated and trained accordingly so as to put their maximum effort on their jobs and this would translate to maximum productivity. According to De Koeijer as cited in Arulrajah (2017) HRM enhances productivity with regards to the organisation’s performance as well as with regards to the employees’ wellbeing, happiness, and health and cordial relationships. They further contend that HRM is of paramount importance in creating mutual gains for both the employer and the employees. Agreeably, Opatha (2015) states that for an organisations to meet the increasing demands of its customers it needs to improve on its productivity and this improvement can only happen through the efforts of the organisation’s most crucial asset, the employee. With increased competition, organisations are forced to improve their productivity and quality while reducing costs and without employees’ involvement and support, the organisations would not succeed and therefore the improvement of productivity and quality is hinged on the employees’ behaviour at work (Opatha 2015).

Productivity is of paramount importance at national level and globally. Arulrajah (2017) contends that a nation’s productivity is the total of productivity of all the organisations making up that nation and it determines the standard of living of that nation, the employment level, the economic growth and the development of that nation. Agreeably, Goetsch and Davis (2000) state that, a nation’s ability to compete globally has a positive effect on the standard of life of its people. According to Goetsch and Davis (2000), the organisation’s ability to compete translates into enhanced productivity and therefore it is crucial for organisations to focus their systems, policies and resources in a manner that will continuously improve both productivity and quality. Having said that, it cannot be over

emphasised that the most valuable organisational asset for enhancing productivity is human resource.

Ortiz et.al (2009) identifies training as part of the three function of Human Resources Management that are related to the quality management principles as developed by Crosby (1979) and Deming (1986). Deming (1986) established the on the job training as a concept that would improve organisational productivity and consistent quality. A study carried out by Glover and Siu (2000) revealed that productivity and quality management within companies were impeded by insufficient HRM systems such as poor standards of training and other HRM functions. Suwandej (2015) avers that successful organisations require management that has five key aspects of Human Resources Management one of which is appropriate Human Resources training.

V. TRAINING AND PRODUCTIVITY

The Business Dictionary defines training as an organised activity aimed at imparting instructions to improve the recipient’s performance while Nassazi (2013) asserts that training refers to planned and systematic activities that are aimed at improving skills, knowledge and competence in performing some tasks. Nassazi (2013) further contends that training is a process of imparting important and necessary skills and appropriate behaviour to enlighten the individuals on the rules and procedures that they should adopt to accomplish their job effectively. Training is part of HRM functions and it assists the organisation and employees in achieving diverse goals some of which are, morale at work, sense of security, employee engagement and other abilities necessary to accomplish a certain task (Rodriguez 2017). According to Elnaga & Imran (2013) training is used to bridge the gaps between current and anticipated performance. Trained employees have the capability of assisting the organisation achieve its competitive advantage in the global market and it is very important for organisations to recognize the importance of employee training if they are to achieve their goals and objectives. Mwema & Gachunga (2014) aver that improved capabilities, knowledge and skills received through training are the cornerstone of the organisation’s competitive edge in today’s global market. Organisations that aspire to be successful through innovation, quality service and improved products can achieve that through trained employees as trained employees are the only ones that would have the capability to envision, develop and implement the strategies as set by the organisational leaders (Nassazi 2013). According to Elnaga & Imran (2013) training is pivoted on enhancing the skills necessary for achieving organisational goals.

VI. THE DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO TRAINING

On the job training- This the kind of training which most employees get as they get into organisations. Knowledge sharing between various departments within the organisation is done through on the job training and it ensures that everyone knows what is happening in other parts off the organisation. This has the advantage of continuous workflow should people in other departments

face some unforeseen challenges impeding them to go to work on a certain period of time. On the job training has different aspects to it some of which are, **job shadowing**, which entails one employee showing another all the different parts of a particular task and this is suitable especially for new employees as part of their induction process (UNESCO 2013). **Coaching** is another aspect of on the job training and it entails line leaders advising subordinates on how to improve their performance and carrying out regular reviews on the employees' performance. This enhances productivity as employees get to learn the best standards of behaviour and performance that result in quality production. **Mentoring** is usually carried out by someone with some special expertise, experience, skill and qualification and it is normally aimed at senior management and offers practical solutions to organisational issues. **Passing on** training entails one person going out to train externally on a train the trainer basis and returning to offer training internally to other employees.

VII. TRAINING AS MOTIVATION FOR EMPLOYEES

Jehanzeb & Bashir (2013) postulate that training enables employees to gain new abilities and skills for personal growth and agreeably, Nassizi (2013) asserts that, most importantly training may be seen as holistic long term growth of employees which results in their ability to perform future roles and responsibilities. This means that employees get motivated when they are trained and motivation obviously leads to effective and efficient productivity. Training helps in reducing frustration experienced in the work place, for instance failure to come up with expected results may lead to demotivation of the employees who may feel discouraged to continue working (Asim 2013). Demotivation coupled with dissatisfaction with one's job might lead to high staff turnover and for this reason organisations that train their workers not only enhance the competencies required to perform the tasks but also assist the worker to feel more satisfied with the results of their performance. Good performance emanating from training motivates the employees and encourage them to keep improving. It improves their competencies, leading to improved performance and retention. Bapna.Langer.Mehra.Gopal& Gupta (2013) contend that employee training and development is an integral part of Human Resources planning activities as it maximises on the individual outputs and may attract perfect talent for the organisation. Elnaga& Imran (2013) concur that training develops thinking capabilities and creativity of the employees resulting in better decision making, customer service, complaints handling and overall self-efficacy. All this leads to an enhanced productivity for the organisation. Job rotation which trains and exposes employees to different tasks within the organisation improves individual capabilities and provides high quality of work at all levels of employees in the organisation. Mel Kleiman as cited in Jehanzeb& Bashir (2013) contends that training increases the probability of individuals to effectively deliver on the organisation's mission. They further assert that when necessary resources are provided to

employees, they become satisfied with their jobs, they become more productive and the organisation becomes more successful. This serves to show that training is necessary for both employee motivation and organisational productivity.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

The review carried out an exploration on how Human Resources training enhance productivity in organisations and it used a systematic review of academic literature on Human Resources Management (HRM) with special emphasis on training as well as on productivity. The review comprised three steps as follows; it developed a data base by carrying out a comprehensive and systematic search to identify and pick literature which is related to HRM training and productivity which was published in peer reviewed academic journals. The second step was to analyse the retrieved articles based on the review which is to determine how training enhances productivity in organisations. It used the analysis to extract descriptive and qualitative facts and information. Lastly the review results and findings were synthesised to answer the research question.

IX. FINDINGS

A. Benefits of Human Resources Training

Training is definitely one of the most important motivators that organisations use to drive both individuals and organisations towards achievement of their short term and long term objectives and goals. Training enhances the overall performance of employees. It enhances knowledge, skills needed to perform organisational task as well as positive attitudes towards achieving the organisational objectives and goals and this translate to enhanced productivity. The following are some of the benefits derived from Human Resources training;

B. Increased productivity through high morale, motivation and confidence

Human Resources training enhances morale of the employees and pushes them to aim high when it comes to the organisational productivity. Motivated employees look forward to going to work and they enjoy working. Confidence derived from the skills and knowledge gained through training enable the employees to produce quality and competitive products. They become more productive because of the skills and knowledge gained from training. Confidence in service offering organisations is of paramount importance as employees with the highest levels of confidence can sell intangible products with ease. Training offers socio emotional support which influences the cognitive and affective states of employees and these lead to greater motivation and increased productivity. Productivity involves the cognitive and affective faculties of the human being over and above the psychomotor faculty.

C. Increased productivity through reduction in production costs

Training empowers employees with the skills and knowledge necessary to perform tasks effectively and efficiently. They gain the knowledge on measurement of some quantities required to come up with certain products and they use appropriate formulae correctly thereby reducing wastes and enhancing productivity. Training of employees result in efficiency in terms or productivity that is more can be produced through less resource utilization.

D. Increased productivity through sense of security among employees

Training gives employees some comfort and confidence that they belong to this organisation. They feel that if the organisation is spending some resources to get them trained, then it means the organisation values them and they feel secure to be in the organisation. This encourages and motivates the employees to work even harder and improve the organisational productivity. As the look forward to going to work due to the increased sense of belonging, absenteeism is done away with and staff turnover reduced leading to high productivity. Training affords employees opportunities for recognition, higher salaries and promotion which increases their morale and motivates them to continue working for this organisation. Training therefore ensure continuous availability of quality labour force needed for the organisation to achieve its objectives and goals. Employees would also achieve higher levels of job satisfaction if they feel that they are part of the organisation and they are investing in their own future and loyalty to the organisation would definitely be enhanced. Employees would thus invest their time and effort in ensuring that the organisation remains profitable and productive.

E. Increased productivity through adaptation to change

Trained employees easily adapt to change, be it change in the systems or ways of doing things, they will always stand ready to embrace the change through the ability to involve themselves in the change process. Training thus provides the competencies necessary to transform according to new and challenging circumstances. Effective management of change will result in continued efforts to improve productivity in the organisation without negative effects emanating from change.

F. Enhanced organisational competitive urge

Organisations that train their employees tend to gain an enhanced competitive urge against their competitors and they tend to increase their market share. This is in line with the study carried out by Jehanzeb and Bashir (2013) who found out that there is a relationship between financing employee training programs and higher revenues from the stock market. This entails that investment in employee training results in gains for the organisation. Organisation tend to retain talent and the most valuable asset, the employees, differentiate themselves against their competitors and improve their brands as best employers thereby enhancing the overall organisational effectiveness and efficiency.

X. CONCLUSION

The objective of this review was to explore how Human Resources training enhances productivity in organisations. Based on the discussions and findings of the review it can safely be concluded that training is an integral part of the Human Resources Management and organisations that want to improve and maintain their competitive urge and improve their market share should not hesitate to finance training activities. Training reduces costs through waste reduction, gives employees a sense of security within the organisation thus building loyalty among employees, motivates employees and enhances their confidence as they carry out their tasks. All this leads to enhanced productivity for the organisation.

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